

IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF MUSIC AS CAM DURING FOETATION THROUGH ULTRASOUND IMAGING

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ABSTRACT : Music therapy used as Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) now a days. Pregnancy is a condition in which mother have to face various psychological and mood changes activates, gynecologist always trying to handle them without using a drug, because drug in form of chemical can affect growth and development of fetus. Many congenital disorders are the result of the use of various types of drugs such as Ectromelia, Phocomelia etc. use in pregnancy. To avoid such conditions gynecologists are always trying to minimize the use of drugs during pregnancy. Antenatal music activities are in the ascendant. The present study is aimed to use the pleasant sounds for emotional regulation, relaxation and pain management, help in parturition, anxiety, stress and facilitate the child's growth and development. Present study proves that if pleasant sounds used scientifically, it will be helpful to control pregnancy mood swing and pain management of mothers and growth and development of fetus. Music increases the unborn child's heartbeat, movement, sound stimulation enhances the brain's maturation, the Mozart effect boosts creativity and cognitive skills, and in utero listening to lullabies improves postnatal sleeping habits. The aim of the study was to evaluate the impact of music therapy on cardiac activity parameters of fetus and movement of fetus through abdominal ultrasonography in antenatal mother in the 8 week to 36 (till delivery) through different types of music (Pop, Classical, Folk, Instrumental, Punjabi, Religious).

Key words : Pregnancy, music therapy, heartbeat, ultrasonography, prenatal sound stimulation, fetal development, parturition.

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INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is one of the remarkable and noble services imposed by nature for the continuity of species results in birth of children. Children's are most valuable gift of nature. A woman face various physiological and psychological problems during pregnancy and child birth. It is a peaceful moment when mother listen and feel fetus heartbeat. Most people use word like to galloping to describe how the heart rate sound. The truth is that a normal fetal heart rate changes during the stage of pregnancy. In normal way at about five-seven week's gestation baby's heart begin to beat and it can be hear by vaginal ultrasound. In present study ultrasounds are conducted at nine week of pregnancy but the impact of music on fetus observed after eighteen week of pregnancy because at this age hearing sense developed well. At this point a normal fetal heart rate is about the same as the mother's' 80 to 85 bpm. From this point, it will increased its rate about three beats per minute per day during the first month of pregnancy. Many other factors

can affect heart rate of an unborn offspring such as music. Fetus also experiences sound from the mother's body outside the womb which impact the development. Scientist agree that in the parental period the fetus is capable of learning, listening. This also gain the support form the story of Abhimanyu in Mahabharata, who is said to have learnt a war skill when he was in the womb of his mother. He could only learn to decode and enter the trap (Chakarvyuh) because by that time her mother felt asleep. Fetus capable to blinking eye during advanced pregnancy, several reactions depend on the type and rhythm of music. Such as pop hip hop music increased the heart rate of fetus while romantic songs increased fetal movement. Music therapy is defined as the controlled use of music, music can heal physiological and psychological & emotional stress of individual during the treatment of an illness or disability.

Pain, mood swings are a normal experience during pregnancy. Mother body is going through physical and hormonal changes affecting their day-to-day life.

Mother having emotional ups and downs. While mood swings are common, depression is a different matter. There is also a difference between feeling nervous and having anxiety that interferes with mother ability to get through the day. Depression and anxiety aren't the same as "mood swings." In fact, there is high evidence that music exerts a positive influence on the fetal development. However, music should not be considered a sort of "panacea." Even though many musical effects on the developing human psychophysiological system are stunning, we have to be careful not to overestimate the power of music and not to ignore underlying mechanisms. Nonetheless, the more we discover how sound, rhythm, neural maturation, cognitive development, and so forth are interrelated, the more "music in antenatal care" gains in medical and educational importance.

Depression or anxiety during pregnancy can increase the risk of experiencing postpartum depression or anxiety. Both depression and anxiety can have adverse health effects on mother and fetus. Music work as a therapy it's brings variety of experiences such as promoting muscular relaxation, relieving anxiety and depression in mother, even fetus also realized and enjoy music therapy, during therapy fetus movement and heartbeat changes. So music can be used to decrease pain or stress during pregnancy and help growth and development of fetus. This study was planned to identify the

- The effect of music therapy on the cardiac activity of a fetus through abdominal ultrasound examination
- The effect of music therapy on the movement of fetus through USG (Ultra sonography)
- The effect of music therapy on "mood swing" of mother

In obstetrics, midwifery, pre- and perinatal education, and developmental psychology, music has become a topic of concern. In many cases, however, interdisciplinary research and antenatal music application go separate ways. Bridging this gap could help to optimize the benefits of antenatal music activities, to control possible sound-associated risks and to create scientifically reliable standards for best practice.

This article intends to contribute to a scientific basis of this promising movement and suggests a multidimensional framework for the use of music therapy in controlling pregnancy mood swing of mother and heartbeat, movement of fetus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Volunteers are selected form Mohan Swaroop Hospital, Dadari, G.B. Nagar. The procedure is

explained to volunteers and they signed their consent form prior to perform the study.

- During study music is provided through two head phone (Wireless headphones having frequency adjusters, sounds meter and Android phone). One head phone was paced on abdomen/womb of mother and another on the ear of mother as shown in Figs. (1, 2, 3). To control the sound frequency, pitch a third headphone is used by instructor. All the three headphones working thorough a single point
- Selected sounds are given to volunteers through headphone and heartbeat, movements are observed through USG machine and ECG of fetus.
- Toshiba (Model Nemio XG) having antenatal facility (scan movement and position of fetus and E.C.G electro cardiograph of fetus) used for the study.
- The study was conducted on twenty eight subjects (volunteer) with pre and post music therapy treatment and repeated twice with every volunteers.
- Music used during study are selected on the basis of DCS theory of neuroendocrine stimulation (Developed by one of the author in 2010). All the volunteers have to fill a questioner for the selection of the music. Hip-hop, religious, romantic, folk of high and low frequency songs are selected on the basis of questioner filled by subject.
- All twenty eight subjects (volunteer) give their consent to perform the study so they are selected. Fifty nine ultrasounds are conducted on these subject during the course of study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In most of the cases heartbeat and movement of fetus increased significantly by music therapy. Variation of heart beat depend on different types of ragas such as pop hip hop music best choice of fetus, music therapy increased heart rate of fetus 5 to 27 BPM it's depend on the nature of fetus. 8 to 9 week fetus also realized the rhythm of music.

Research work was conducted on volunteer pregnant women's to measure cardiac activity of fetus through abdominal ultrasound to give music therapy (different types of ragas). The findings are significant and highly significant.

There are highly valid quality standards for antenatal, perinatal and postnatal health care. They refer crucially to the control of physiological and mental risk factors such as hypertension in pregnancy or depressive dispositions. From this perspective, we understand music therapy as an add-on intervention, as a way to facilitate

health promotion as well as preventive measures, and to improve individual and social well-being. We found variation of heart beat depend on the different types of sounds such as pop, hip hop music is one of the best choice of fetus, the sound of music increase the heart rate of fetus 5-27 bpm it's depend on the nature of fetus. 8 to 9 week's fetus also realized the rhythm of music. Fetus react according to the choice of mother (i.e) if mother enjoyed during therapy so murmured of heart beat increased. Mother age and mentality also play a key role in the fetus activity. Some of the mothers are religious in nature so their fetus movement increased through religious music (bhajan or qawwalees). Romantic songs are the second choice of fetus, when mother hear romantic song, the heart rate of fetus have increased at few points but fetus moved faster with the rhythm of hip hop music, mostly fetus shows bicycling movement (of both feet called stepping and stepping) during therapy, which is very important in helping to turn the baby upside down for a normal delivery. So music given during pregnancy will be helpful in parturition. Even few fetus shows half cycling movement through folk dancing songs in advanced pregnancy (32 weeks or more till delivery). 8 to 9 week fetus also starting rolling movement during therapy. When antenatal mother and fetus both treated with romantic music, the movement of fetus slow down according to romantic music but the murmured of heart increased magnificently.

The vigorous movement of fetus may have painful in some women's but maximum women's admitted in survey that during music therapy pain of vigorous movement of fetus measurably decreased and they feel relaxed during and after therapy. Mostly women admitted that classical dancing songs play a major role to decrease pain of vigorous half cyclic or rolling movement of fetus. Pain in lower abdomen is a major problem of mostly women's, which is decreased by music therapy in many cases during and after therapy.

Table 1 data reflects that in both IInd and IIIrd trimester the heartbeat increased significantly. The rate of increase in heart beat is higher IInd trimester in comparison to IIIrd trimester. In IInd trimester heartbeat of fetus increased significantly (0.128) to highly significant (0.006) at $p < 0.5$. In IInd trimester there is -ve correlation between pregnancy week and heartbeat, which reflects with pregnancy the heart beat decreases in IInd trimester, while in IIIrd trimester heart beat increases with pregnancy, shows a positive correlation.

Findings of Table 2 reflects that the movement of fetus increases in Ist, IInd and IIIrd trimester, but this increase is significant in IInd and IIIrd trimester. Sound impact on mother to control anxiety is significant in all three trimesters.

In first trimester (upto 14 week) of pregnancy (5 volunteers with 10 therapy), the heart beat is not easy to hear. In all cases low sound, week murmur and normal

Table 1 : Showing impact of sound on heart beat.

Trimester	N	Hear beat pre and post therapy	Correlation between pregnancy week & heartbeat of fetus	Correlation between age of mother & heartbeat of fetus	Correlation between pregnancy week & difference of heartbeat of fetus	Correlation between age of mother & difference of heartbeat of fetus
Columns	n	6 and 7	5 and 7	4 and 7	5 and 8	4 and 8
II-Trimester (14-28 Week)	20	0.128268951	-0.43661	0.451339	0.170739	0.042007
III-Trimester (29-36 Week)	29	0.006354003	0.166583	-0.04487	0.307107	-0.04649

$p < .05$

Table 2 : Showing impact of sound fetus movement and mother mood.

Trimester	n	Fetus Movement				Mother response			
		No change	Increase	P Value $p < .05$ (I to III Trimester)	P Value $p < .05$ (II to III Trimester)	No change	Relax	P Value $p < .05$ (I to III Trimester)	P Value $p < .05$ (II to III Trimester)
I-Trimester (9-13.5 week)	10	9	1	0.331939	0.212723	2	8	0.051954	0.068782
II-Trimester (14-28 week)	20	9	11			2	18		
III-Trimester (29-36 week)	29	6	23			2	27		

Fig. 1 : Ultrasonography (Pres and post music therapy) of volunteer number-7 in which movement and heartbeat increased and mother feel relaxed.

Fig. 2 : Ultrasonography (Pre and post music therapy) of volunteer number-10 in which movement and heartbeat increased and mother feel relaxed.

Fig. 3 : Showing positional placemats during music therapy of volunteers.

murmur sounds are observed, which is increased after music therapy with high volume. The movements of fetus are also observed. The common problems reported by the mothers in first trimester are vomiting, itching in vaginal part and abdominal pain. In all cases mother feel

relax and happy during and after music therapy treatment.

In second trimester (15-27 week) of pregnancy, (10 volunteers with 20 therapy) significant increase in heartbeat of fetus is observed at high sound frequency (8 cases) and significant decrease (significance level 0.05)

in heartbeat of fetus is observed at low sound frequency (6 cases).

In third trimester (25-36 week) of pregnancy, (14 volunteers with 29 therapy) significant increase in heartbeat of fetus is observed at high sound frequency (23 cases) and decrease in heartbeat of fetus is observed at low sound frequency (6 cases).

Similarly the response of mother to music found highly significant in all there trimester. Out of 69 treatments mother found to be relaxed in 63 cases. The music relaxed them and handle their mood swing and pain of pregnancy.

Significant findings

Fetus moved faster during hip-hop and romantic songs which reflects that fetus enjoying it. Increased blood pressure and fast breath of fetus show during hip hop music (DJ remix songs). Slow paced music leads to lower heart rate comparison to their baseline values. The soft sound of romantic songs with low rhythm are perfect for fetus or infants. The increase in bicycling movement observed during hip-hop and stepping movement increased in romantic songs. Music positively impact the health of adults or infants but pain or stress during pregnancy have decreased few points by music therapy (i.e music decreased the level of stress during pregnancy), which results to control the pregnancy mood swing of the mother. The mother voice and reactions is one of the most important sensual stimuli for the fetus. Music also help to overcome delivery pain through DCS theory of neuroendocrine stimulation.

- Music therapy increased heart rate of fetus 5 to 27 BPM it's depend on the nature of fetus. 8 to 9 week fetus also realized the rhythm of music although hearing senses are developed in 18th week. It may be due to pressure effect of sound.
- Pop hip hop music increased the heart rate of fetus while romantic songs increased fetal movement
- Music is helpful to control the “mood swing” syndrome of mother
- The soft sound of romantic songs with low rhythm are perfect for fetus or infants.
- Music decreased the level of stress during pregnancy.
- Music also help to overcome delivery pain and easy parturition.
- Music is helpful to increase the rocking movement of fetus, which intern helpful in the growth and development of fetus
- Classical dancing songs play a major role to decrease pain of vigorous half cyclic or rolling movement of

fetus.

- Pain in lower abdomen is decreased by music therapy in many cases during and after therapy.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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